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AIR POLLUTION MODELLING-SOFTWARE – A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Applications of various air pollution modeling software like MEASURE, COLE, OFFROAD, URBEMIS, MOBILE, PART5, MOBTOX, SPOT, PEMS, OEMS, EMFAC series of models have been discussed in this paper.

Keywords: Fuel Efficiency Automobile Test (FEAT), Geographic Information System (GIS), Traffic Control Management Systems (TCMS), Transportation Improvement Plans (TIPs), New Generation Models (NGMs), Remote Sensing Devices (RSDs).

1.0 AIR POLLUTION MODELING SOFTWARE

Irregular growth patterns of suburbs, population growth are of many factors which gave rise to pollution problems in U.S. metros. Striking a balance between development and maintaining ambient

pollutant levels within the limits is possible by continually building up innovative approaches to keep air pollution under control. Mobile Emission Assessment System for Urban and Regional Evaluation (MEASURE) assists researchers in evaluating new mobile emission mitigation strategies. MEASURE is a GIS based model and uses model emission rates and operation. Understanding the relationship between characteristics of transportation system and emission production is crucial for devising strategies for mitigation of air pollution. The existing process of motor vehicle emission modeling is based on four separate models, but this system has its own drawbacks like the estimates of vehicle activity lack special resolution (Bachman W.H. 1998). Exponential growth of the population creates a lot of demand, and hence puts enormous stress on the natural resources for energy and other necessities. This has a direct bearing on the emissions of the green house gases (GHGs) viz. Carbon dioxide (CO₂), Nitrous Oxide (N₂O), Methane (CH₄), Hydro fluorocarbons (HFCs), Per fluorocarbons (PFCs), Sulphur hexafluoride (SF₆) and thus their concentration is also increasing rapidly.

Air pollutants like SO_x, reactive organic gases (ROGs), and particulate matter (PM), indirectly add to the greenhouse gas effect. One of the major adverse impacts of GHGs is the destruction of the ozone layer in the stratospheric region, which acts as a UV radiation shield. Excessive direct exposure to UV rays causes different types of skin and eye diseases. Carbon Footprint Estimation Tool (CFET) is an efficient tool for the estimation of GHG emissions. This tool assists the developers of construction industries to take greener decisions, thus reduces the carbon foot print of these projects. Quantification of emissions for individual processes can be done by the use of various tools like NONROAD2008, COLE, and OFFROAD2007; for variety of sources URBEMIS and Palate can be used (Melanta et al. 2013). Air quality officials and consultants can use NONROAD Model for estimation of air pollution inventories (USEPA 2009). Carbon Online Estimator (COLE) generates carbon estimates based on forest inventory data [United States Department of Agriculture (USDA), Forest Service, Northern Research Station (NRS) 2011]. Inventory data of emissions for off-road mobile sources can be generated by using OFFROAD2007 [Air Resource Board (ARB), California Environmental Protection Agency (CEPA) 2007]. URBEMIS estimates air emissions from land use development projects. It uses the California Air Resources Board's EMFAC2007 model for on-road vehicle emissions and the OFFROAD2007 model for off-road vehicle emissions [URBEMIS Environmental Management Software (EMS) 2007].

Using on-vehicle testing, remote emission analyzers can be calibrated, compliance of vehicles operating with alternative fuels can be adhered to, and realistic mobile source emission models can be developed (USEPA 2002). Portable Emissions Measurement System (PEMS) is a better model to quantify real world duty cycles and emission rates. Real world data has to be used in the verification and evaluation of vehicular emissions under actual operating conditions. Reduction in the fuel use and thus the emissions can be achieved by transforming the operational procedures of construction vehicles. Green fleet certification programs have to be developed in order to have real world assessments. Projections of air pollutant emissions have to be input with inventories of pollutant emissions. University environmental and construction faculty should incorporate the environmental impacts of projects into engineering curricula (Lewis et al. 2009). Precise assessment values of motor-vehicle emissions are prerequisite for the successful implementation of air-quality improvement program. Mobile Sources Emission (MOBILE) model is EPA's key tool not only to estimate emissions viz. CO, VOCs, and NO_x, of on-road mobile sources but also for the related EIA. PART5 and MOBTOX models are used to estimate particulate matter and air toxics. The estimates of factors of emission are made in grams per mile. Varied factors involved in estimating include vehicles' condition, type, age; emission control systems' performance; fuel composition; meteorological conditions, traffic patterns, spatial and temporal resolution etc. MOBILE has its own drawbacks e.g. under-estimation of VOCs. These are rectified in MOBILE6 which is a far more superior and refined model (NAP 2000).

Simple, Portable, On-Vehicle Testing (SPOT) is used by USEPA for non-road equipment and other models are also continuously improved. PEMS is easy to install on wide variety of vehicles, weather and tamper proof, consumes low power, able to communicate remotely, has fast- response sensors and stand-alone flow measurement facility, etc (USEPA 2002). Real-time vehicle tailpipe emissions are measured

using portable on-board instruments. Precision of data of measurement of on-board emissions must be ensured for developing New Generation Models (NGMs). EMFAC series of models are used in California. CO and HC emissions are greatly affected by various acceleration modes. Georgia Institute of Technology's MEASURE is like a model of emission mapping. The modal emissions model developed by the Center for Environmental Research and Technology at University of California Riverside (UCR-CERT) predicts second by-second tailpipe emissions and fuel consumption for different vehicle categories in different states of condition. Before adopting Neural Network Method, the network has to be trained extensively and appropriately. To develop an NGM three approaches are considered: (1) Use of high frequency data (2) Use of statistical methods. (3) Development of Extensive Data Set and use of ERE; a combination of the approaches is also considered.

The New Generation Model (NGM) - Multi-scale Motor Vehicle and Equipment Emission System (MOVES) is the successor to the MOBILE6 highway vehicle emission factor model. MOVES model is based on OEMS data. Data collected from onboard emissions measurement devices is the input to MOVES. While estimating emissions at multiple scales, consistent emission rates across the analysis scales are required. Direct data-driven methodologies have many advantages like similar approaches can be used for different vehicle types or for different pollutants (USEPA 2002). Fieldwork and data processing helps in framing a robust Quality Assurance Procedure (QAP). OEM supports multiple study objectives. The accuracy of estimation of average emissions depends upon intra-vehicle variability. The real-world vehicle emissions and fuel use are episodic in nature. Traffic Control Management Systems (TCMS) and Transportation Improvement Plans (TIPs) reduce the frequency and duration of episodic events. Therefore by better traffic management, vehicular emissions can be reduced. Onboard systems are significant for temporal and spatial real-world emissions' measurement. But OEM studies are challenged by uncontrollable nature of traffic flow. Estimates of uncertainty convey information regarding the quality of the emission factors and serve as a basis for calculation of uncertainty in emission inventories (Frey et al. 2003).

2.0 SIGNIFICANCE OF GIS BASED MODELS

Geographic Information System (GIS) is well-suited to model emissions of mobile sources, as the emissions can be interconnected with coordinates of time and space. GIS is an excellent tool to facilitate the communication of results to policy makers, public and other stake holders (Bachman et al. 1996). Using a remote sensor system in conjunction with video free-frame system, the vehicular carbon monoxide CO emissions' data superimposed on the corresponding license plates was obtained instantaneously. Federal Testing Procedure (FTP) indicated that a very good correlation exists between measurement of emissions CO and Hydrocarbon (HC) using a remote sensing program. But such a correlation doesn't exist for NO_x emissions with CO or HC emissions. There are umpteen techniques to efficiently use the remote sensing information for air pollution control measures. The remote sensing devices for measuring vehicular air pollutants can be placed at specific locations such as toll-gates to check the vehicles and take necessary steps to control pollution. An infrared remote monitoring system for automobile carbon monoxide exhaust emissions was developed by the University of Denver with the support from the Colorado Office of Energy Conservation. This system is also called as the Fuel Efficiency Automobile Test (FEAT) (Stedman et al. 1990). Instrument that remotely measures the CO emissions from thousand of vehicles per day with a sensitivity of ± 1 percent CO in the exhaust was used in Denver, Colorado in January 1989. The remote sensor could be used as an effective surveillance tool to identify high CO-emitting vehicles (Lawson 1990). The study noted a clear higher emission rates from older vehicles (Cadle et al. 1991).

A pilot program application of on-road remote sensing was carried out at two locations in Provo, Utah during the winter period of 1991-92 to identify repeat gross polluting vehicles. It was noted that around fifty percent of the total carbon monoxide emissions were emitted from only about 10 percent of the vehicles (Bishop et al. 1993). The difficulties involved in the application of remote sensing (RS) technology in the tunnel environments have led to the improvements in the RS technology. Prototype periscope system was successfully used for the measurements of dual lane traffic (Bishop et al. 1994). Infrared

remote sensing was used to characterize the on-road emissions from the school buses and other types of buses in North Carolina. The uses of remote sensing are manifold in nature like improving inspection and maintenance programs, obtaining instantaneous measurements of tailpipe emissions etc. (Frey et al. 1997). The cost effectiveness of Remote Sensing Devices (RSDs) for the identification and repair of vehicles with high emissions is carried out in 1990s by the USEPA (USEPA 1994).

REFERENCES

1. Air Resource Board (ARB), CEPA. (2007). "User's Guide for OFFROAD2007." www.arb.ca.gov/msei/offroad/pubs/users_guide_b.doc (Aug. 19, 2013).
2. Austin, T., DiGenova, F., and Carlson, T. (1994). "Analysis of the Effectiveness and Cost-Effectiveness of Remote Sensing Devices." USEPA.
3. Bachman, W., Sarasua, V., and Guensler, R. (1996). "Geographic Information System Framework for Modeling Mobile-Source Emissions." Transportation Research Record 1551, NAP.
4. Bachman W.H. (1998). "A GIS-Based Modal Model of Automobile Exhaust Emissions." Prepared by Georgia Institute of Technology for USEPA. <http://nepis.epa.gov/Adobe/PDF/9100S90X.pdf> (Nov. 16, 2013).
5. Bishop, G. A., Zhang, Y., McLaren, S. E., Guenther, P. L., Beaton, S. P., Peterson, J. E., Stedman, D. H., Pierson, W. R., Knapp, K. T., Zweidinger, R. B., Duncan, J. W., and McArver, A. Q. (1994), "Enhancements of Remote Sensing for Vehicle Emissions in Tunnels", *J. Air & Waste Manage. Assoc.*, 44(2), 169-175.
6. Bishop, G.A., Stedman, D. H., Peterson J.E., Hosick, T. J., and Guenther, P. L. (1993), "A Cost-Effectiveness Study of Carbon Monoxide Emissions Reduction Utilizing Remote Sensing," *J. Air & Waste Manage. Assoc.*, 43(7):978-988.
7. Cadle, S. H., and Stephens, R. D. (1991), "Remote Sensing Measurements of Carbon Monoxide Emissions from On-Road Vehicles", *J. Air & Waste Manage. Assoc.*, 41(1), 39-46.
8. European Commission. (2013). "The EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS)." http://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/ets/index_en.htm (Aug. 21, 2013).
9. EIA. (2013). "International Energy Statistics." <http://goo.gl/cvb16V> (Sep. 20, 2013).
10. Frey, H.C. and Eichenberger, D.A. (1997). "Remote Sensing of Mobile Source Air Pollutant Emissions: Variability and Uncertainty in On-Road Emissions Estimates of Carbon Monoxide and Hydrocarbons for School and Transit Buses." Prepared by North Carolina State University for North Carolina Department of Transportation, Raleigh.
11. Frey, H. and Bammi, S. (2003). "Probabilistic Nonroad Mobile Source Emission Factors." *J. Environ. Eng.*, 129(2), 162-168.
12. Frey, H. C., Unal, A., Roupail, N. M., and Colyar, J. D. (2003). "On-Road Measurement of Vehicle Tailpipe Emissions Using a Portable Instrument." *J. Air & Waste Manage. Assoc.*, 53, 992-1002.
13. Lawson, D. R., Groblicki, P. J., Stedman, D. H., Bishop, G. A., Guenther, P. L. (1990). "Emissions from in-use motor vehicles in Los Angeles: A Pilot Study of Remote Sensing and the Inspection and Maintenance Program", *J. Air & Waste Manage. Assoc.*, 40(8), 1096-1105.

14. Lewis, P., Rasdorf, W., Frey, H. C., Pang, S. H., & Kim, K. (2009). "Requirements and incentives for reducing construction vehicle emissions and comparison of nonroad diesel engine emissions data sources." *J. Constr. Eng. Manage.*, 135(5), 341-351.
15. Lin, J., Youn, D., Liang, X., and Wuebbles, D. (2008). "Global model simulation of summertime U.S. ozone diurnal cycle and its sensitivity to PBL mixing, spatial resolution, and emissions." *Atmos. Environ.*, 42(36), 8470-8483.
16. Melanta, S., Miller-Hooks, E., and Avetisyan, H. (2013). "Carbon Footprint Estimation Tool for Transportation Construction Projects." *J. Constr. Eng. Manage.*, 139(5), 547-555.
17. Stedman, D. H., Bishop, G. A. (1990). "An Analysis of On-Road Remote Sensing as a Tool for Automobile Emissions Control." *Final report to the Illinois Department of Energy and Natural Resources*. ILENR/RE-AQ-90/05.
18. The National Academic Press (NAP), National Research Council. (2000). "Modeling Mobile-Source Emissions." Washington, D.C.
19. NRS, Forest Service, USDA. (2011). "COLE (Carbon OnLine Estimator)." {<http://www.nrs.fs.fed.us/carbon/tools/#cole>} (Aug. 19, 2013).
20. URBEMIS. (2007). "Environmental Management Software." {<http://www.urbemis.com/software/URBEMIS9%20Users%20Manual%20Main%20Body.pdf>} (Aug. 19, 2013).
21. USEPA - OTAQ. (2002). "Draft Design and Implementation Plan for EPA's Multi-Scale Motor Vehicle and Equipment Emission System (MOVES)." {<http://www.epa.gov/otaq/models/ngm/p02006.pdf>} (Nov. 29, 2013).
22. USEPA. (2002). "EPA's Onboard Emissions Analysis Shootout: Overview and Results." {<http://epa.gov/otaq/models/ngm/r02026.pdf>} (Oct. 29, 2013).
23. USEPA. (2002). "Health Assessment Document For Diesel Engine Exhaust." {<http://goo.gl/RAOIms>} (Oct. 25, 2013).
24. USEPA - OTAQ. (2002). "Methodology for Developing Modal Emission Rates for EPA's Multi-Scale Motor Vehicle and Equipment Emission System" {<http://www.epa.gov/otaq/models/ngm/r02027.pdf>} (Nov. 16, 2013)
25. USEPA. (2002). "On-Road, In-Use Emissions Test Systems." {<http://www.epa.gov/oar/caaac/mstrs/wilson.pdf>} (Oct. 25, 2013).
26. USEPA. (2002). "PEMS On-Vehicle Measurement Strategy." {<http://oica.net/wp-content/uploads/us-eap-status-of-pems.pdf>} (Oct. 26, 2013).
27. USEPA - OTAQ. (2002); Frey, H. C. et al. "Recommended Strategy for On-board Emission Data Analysis and Collection for the New Generation Model."
28. USEPA. (2009). "NONROAD Model." {<http://www.epa.gov/otaq/nonrdmdl.htm>} (Aug. 19, 2013).